

Assessment of Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Hospital nurses

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ABSTRACT

Background: Work-related Musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are one of the major occupational health problems in nursing professional that is characterized as multifactorial. The aim of the study was to assess the prevalence and risk factors contributing to WMSDs among hospital nurses. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 70 hospital nurses working in tertiary care hospital of Eastern Uttar Pradesh. The validated self-structured questionnaire was used to estimate the prevalence and risk factors of WMSDs by using random sampling technique. The socio demographic and occupational information were also obtained from hospital nurses. **Result:** The results revealed that 66 out of 70 hospital nurses had reported pain and discomfort in any of these nine body regions (lower back, knees, shoulder, neck, ankle/feet, upper back, hip/thigh, wrist/hand, and elbows). The commonest region of pain and discomfort was found in low back (64.3%), then in knees (52.9%) and in shoulder (42.9%). WMSDs have significant relationship at $p < 0.05$ with age, marital status, number of children, professional qualification, BMI, level of tiredness and working with vibrating tools. **Conclusion:** Work place influences the development of WMSDs among hospital nurses. Educational programmes on prevention and coping strategies for WMSDs may be implied to reduce the rate of occupational hazards and promote efficiency in patient care.

Key words: Work related musculoskeletal disorders, Musculo skeletal discomforts, Hospital nurses, Occupational health.

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Introduction

Musculoskeletal disorders are commonest occupational health problem at the work place world wide. It is common in workers of many occupations like catering industry¹, handicraft workers², farming³, construction workers⁴, office workers⁵ etc but health care workers are mostly affected. In the healthcare sector, prevalence rates of Work related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WMSDs) ranges from 28% to 96% over a one-year time period including those among nurses.⁶ Work related Musculoskeletal Disorders encompasses a group of inflammatory and degenerative conditions that results from a work-related event and affects the muscles, tendons, ligaments, joints, peripheral nerves, and supporting blood vessels with consequent ache, pain or discomfort.⁷ WMSDs have been listed as occupational disorders by International Labour Organization (ILO) since 1960.⁸ According to National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), a federal agency of US responsible for collecting, analyzing and interpreting information, conducting scientific research for the prevention of work related injury and illness have classified WMSDs as the second most common occupational disorder, after occupational respiratory diseases.⁹ These work related Musculo-skeletal disorders account for nearly 48% of all diseases¹⁰.

According to reported data, nurses have a very high prevalence of WMSDs worldwide, for example, in Europe, from 10% to 50% in France¹¹, 89% in Portugal¹²; in USA 35.1% to 47%¹³ and 80.8% in Uganda¹⁴; and in 78.6% in China¹⁵, 85% in Saudi

Arabia¹⁶, and 88% in Iran.¹⁷ In a recent study, more than half of the nurses (54%) showed WMSDs in the lower back, followed by neck (41%), shoulder (34%), and hand-wrist (26%).¹⁸ In a clinical setting, nursing personnel often has to exert physically for moving patients or equipment from one location to another, and such activities involve excessive bending or turning or over stretching of the body leading to painful conditions. It also significantly impacts the quality of life of the nurses. It causes more absenteeism, increased work restriction, low productivity, burn out or disability among nurses than any other group of diseases. It also has financial impact considerably on the individual, on the organization, and on the society.

The work-related musculoskeletal problem commonly prevailing in hospital nurses is generally related to the body regions-neck, shoulder, upper back; lower back, knees, ankles/feet, hip/thighs, etc. Kalkim, Midilli, and Dogru conducted a survey on 498 nurses with WMSDs. Their results indicated that the body locations with the highest prevalence rates were the lower back (78.5%), back (74.9%), knee joint (63.1%), neck (61.2%), and shoulder (59.6%)¹⁹. Chen et al, investigated musculoskeletal discomfort among nurses at 793 medical centres, and their results indicated that 63.5% had neck pain, 62.6% had shoulder pain, and 59.3% had lower back pain²⁰.

It is evident from several studies that the individual attributes, its life style the working conditions are the prime factors which contributes to the development of WMSDs. According to Chen et al. indicated that influential factors that contribute to WMSDs include age, work seniority, work content, working hours, number of hours worked per week, amount of time standing or walking during work, stress levels from work, and exercise habits²¹. Ko et al. discovered a significant correlation between turning or moving patients and pain and discomfort in the lower back²².

It is important to understand the prevalence and risk factors associated with WMSDs among nurses for health administrators and health-care workers to curtail the existence of the problem. Thus, the distribution of WMSDs among nurses must be determined. In this study, the prevalence of WMSDs and the risk factors among nurses was explored. Results from this study can serve as a reference for nursing administrators and health administrators in reducing musculoskeletal discomfort among nurses and thereby achieving improved nursing quality and performance. There had been no previous study done in our hospital to assess the WMSDs among nurses. Hence a need arises to assess WMSDs among hospital nurses. The objective of the study is to assess the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder related to the work among hospital nurses and to identify the risk factors contributing to WMSDs among hospital nurses.

Objective

1. To assess the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder related to the work among hospital nurses.
2. To identify the risk factors contributing to WMSDs among hospital nurses.

Operational definition

Prevalence - Prevalence is a statistical concept referring to the number of cases of a disorder that are present in a particular population at a particular time. In this study, number of nurses reported to have pain or discomfort in any nine regions of body part which are included in the study at the point of time.

Risk factors- It is a variable associated with an increased risk of disease or injury. In this study, personal characteristics (socio-demographic variables, occupational profile, health status & life style pattern) and work conditions are taken as risk factor causing WMSDs.

Delimitation: This study is limited to the assessment of the WMSDs among nursing personnel who were providing direct patient care. This research study is limited to risk factors of personal characteristics and working condition. It does not address any psychological and organizational factors which may cause WMSDs.) need to be deleted.

Methods

A Cross-sectional design was used to assess prevalence and risk factors of Work-related Musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) among the nurses of tertiary care hospital in Varanasi. A self-administered questionnaire survey was employed. The nurses working in general medicine, surgical department, intensive care unit, coronary care unit, operation theatres, casualty unit and specialized wards were included in the study.

The including criteria for participants were as follows: (1) registered nurses who are working in the hospital for more than one year (2) those who do not have MSD due to disease condition, and (3) were willing to participate in the study. Total 70 nurses participated the study. The tools included in the study for data gathering consisted of socio-demographic details and questionnaire on personal characteristics (occupational profile, health status & life style pattern) and work conditions. The collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics and association was observed using chi square test.

Reliability of tool: The internal consistency of the instrument was measured using Cronbach’s alpha which was 0.84. It shows that the instrument used for the study is reliable.

Results

The findings of the study are divided into following sections:

Section 1- Description of socio-demographic, occupational profile and life style pattern of hospital nurses.

Section 2- Description of risk factors of WMSDs among hospital nurses. (deleted)

Section 2- Assessment of work-related musculoskeletal disorder related pain and discomfort in nine body regions.

Section3- Association between socio-demographic variables and WMSDs.

Section 4- Association between risk factors and WMSDs.

Section -1: Description of socio-demographic and occupational profile and life style pattern of hospital nurses:

The Table-1 showed that the majority of respondents 47.1% were within the age group of 31-40 and 31.4% were in 21-30 age groups, 21.4% were in age group of more than 40 years. Out of the respondents, 68.6 % were married 31.4% were single; and 72.9% were females while the remaining 27.1% were males. About 51.4% of the respondents belong to the nuclear family and rest 48.6% belong to joint family; 68.6% of the respondents have professional qualification of GNM and 31.4% were graduate and above.54.3% of respondents have no or one child and 45.7% have 2 or more than 2 children. The maximum number of respondent (55.7%) commute by two-wheeler and 30 % by walk rest 14.2% by private car and auto rickshaw.

Table-1: Socio-demographic of Hospital Nurses

Socio-demographic profile of the Nurses		No.	%
Age (in years)	21-30	22	31.4
	31-40	33	47.1
	>40	15	21.4
Gender	Male	19	27.1
	Female	51	72.9
Professional Qualification	GNM	48	68.6
	Post basic BSc Nursing	5	7.1
	BSc Nursing & above	17	24.3
Marital status	Married	55	68.6
	Unmarried	15	31.4
No of children	0-1	38	54.3
	More than 2	32	45.7
Types of family	Joint	34	48.6
	Nuclear	36	51.4
Means of transportation	By walk	21	30.0
	Auto/ Rickshaw	5	7.1
	Scooter/Bike	39	55.7
	Car	5	7.1

Table-2 showed occupational profile of nurses which included the type of ward and hours of work performed in assigned ward. It was found that 57.1% of the respondents were working in General ward whereas rest 42.9 % were posted in critical care and operation theatre. 35.7% of the respondent had 0-2 years of work experience and rest 64.3% had more than 2 years of work experience in present ward. 50% of nurses had total experience of 10 years or less and remaining 50% had more than 10years of total experience. Numbers of patients assigned per day were more than 15 to the 68.6% of the nurses and total working hours per day including hours at home was more than 12 hours among 50% of the respondents.

Table-2: Occupational Profile of the Hospital Nurses

Occupational Profile of the Nurses		No.	%
Ward	General Ward	40	57.1
	ICU/CCU	11	15.7
	Casualty	9	12.9
	OT	10	14.3
Working experience in present ward (in Years)	0-2	25	35.7
	2-4	20	28.6
	4-6	13	18.6
	>6	12	17.1
Total working experience (in years)	1-10	35	50.0
	10-20	26	37.1
	>20	9	12.9
No. of patient assigned per day	1-15	12	31.4
	>15	48	68.6
Total Working hours per day (in hours)	8-10	26	37.1
	10-12	9	12.9
	12-14	21	30.0
	>14	14	20.0

Table-3 describes the health profile and life style pattern of hospital nurses.62.8% of nurses had normal BMI and haemoglobin level. 77.1% were having good health status and 57.1% mentioned that they feel tired at the end of the work at hospital. 15.7 % reported that they had health complains recently and 18.6% were having one or the other chronic disease. Just 2.9% had suffered from any injury. 38.6% of the nurses reported that they do exercises to keep themselves physically fit and 31.4% do jogging, 11.4% do yoga and 17.1 % do other physical activity for maintaining their health. 57.1% take a 6 hours' sleep and rest 42.9% take more than 6 hours of sleep, 72.9% love to do indoor activity during leisure time.

Table -3: Health Profile and life style pattern of Hospital Nurses

Health Profile of the Nurses		No.	%
BMI (in kg/m ²)	18.5-25.0	44	62.8
	25-30	26	37.1
Hemoglobin (mg/dl)	8 - 10 mg/dl	26	37.1
	12-14 mg/dl	44	62.8
Health status (self Reported)	Good	54	77.1
	Average	16	22.8
Tiredness at the end of the work at hospital (self Reported)	Not tired	12	17.1
	A bit tired	18	25.7
	Tired	35	50.0
	Very tired	5	7.1
Recently any health complains	Yes	11	15.7
	No	58	82.9
Any chronic disease	Yes	13	18.6
	No	57	81.4
Suffered from any injury	Yes	2	2.9
	No	68	97.1
Life Style pattern of Nurses			
Physical activity	Jogging	22	31.4
	Yoga	8	11.4
	Exercise	27	38.6
	Other	12	17.1
Activities in leisure time	Indoor activities	51	72.9
	Outdoor activity	19	27.1
Sleeping hours	6 hours	40	57.1
	7 hours	21	30.0
	8 hours & more	9	12.9

Figure-1: Bar Diagram showing percentage of the type of work done by Hospital Nurses in Clinical area.

Figure-1 describes the kind of work the nurses perform in clinical area. 37% of nurses reported that they have to work almost always in standing position for long period of time, 43% mentioned that sometime they need to work in sitting position for long period of time, 26% of nurses reported that sometimes they need to move heavy load at workplace. Frequent exertion of arms and hands is often observed by 34% of nurses, working in uncomfortable postured almost always is reported by 19% and 30% mentioned that they have to work in same position for long period of time almost always.

Figure-2: Bar Diagram Showing Work Conditions of Hospital Nurses in Clinical Area

In Figure 2, bar diagram showed various work condition in which nurses have to work in their respective clinical area. 94% nurses reported that they have to climb stairs at working place, 23% nurses reported that they walk on irregular surfaces, 7% about working with vibrating tools, working in insufficient space by 54%, insufficient height to reach things by 7%, presence of tangling cords by 23%, slippery floor observed by 34% and 13% reported slip or fall during work.

Section-2: Assessment of work-related musculoskeletal disorder related pain and discomfort in nine body regions.

The study showed the prevalence of work related Musculo-skeletal disorder among 64 (91.42%) out of 70 (100%) hospital nurses.

In Table 4, prevalence of WMSDs in different nine body region is shown. The most prevalent area of the body where the nurses perceived pain and discomfort due to WMSDs is lower back (64.3%), then knees (52.9%), 42.9% in shoulder and 40.0% in neck. Least number of nurses perceived pain in elbows (5.7%) region.

Table- 4: Prevalence of WMSDs in different nine body region

Pain or discomfort in body region	Absent		Present	
	No.	%	No.	%
Neck	42	60.0	28	40.0
Upper back	48	68.0	22	32.0
Lower back	25	35.7	45	64.3
Shoulder	40	57.1	30	42.9
Elbows	66	94.3	4	5.7
Wrist/hand	57	81.4	13	18.6
Hips/thighs	52	74.3	18	25.7
Knees	33	47.1	37	52.9
Ankle/feet	46	65.7	24	34.3

Intensity of pain and discomfort perceived by hospital nurses according to body region is shown in Table-5. The severe and moderate pain is observed by 17.1% and 30% of nurses in lower back respectively. Mild pain was reported by 25.7% of nurses in shoulder and neck (24.3%).

Table- 5: Intensity of pain and discomfort among nurses

Location	Mild		Moderate		Severe	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Neck	17	24.3	8	11.5	3	4.2
Upper back	16	23.0	4	5.6	2	2.9
Lower back	12	17.1	21	30.0	12	17.1
Shoulder	18	25.7	10	14.2	2	3.0
Elbows	2	2.8	2	2.9	0	0.0
Wrist/hands	5	7.1	6	8.6	2	2.9
Hips/thighs	6	8.6	12	17.1	0	0.0
Knees	15	21.4	17	24.3	5	7.1
Ankles/feet	13	18.6	10	14.3	1	1.4

Section – 3: Association between socio-demographic variables and WMSDs

Table- 6: Association between Socio-Demographic variables and WMSDs

Socio-demographic variables		WMSDs present		t2 Test	P value
		No.	%		
Age	21-30	16	25.0	14.318	0.003
	31-40	33	51.6		
	>40	15	23.4		
Sex	Male	16	25.0	1.734	0.188
	Female	48	75.0		
Family	Joint	30	46.9	0.860	0.354
	Nuclear	34	53.1		
Professional Qualification	GNM	46	71.9	3.781	0.05
	BSc N/, PB/ BSc N./MSc. N.	18	28.1		
No. of Children	0-1	33	51.6	2.231	0.013
	2 or >2	31	48.4		
Transportation	By walk	18	28.1	1.250	0.264
	By any other means for transport	46	71.9		
Marital Status	Married	54	84.4	14.937	0.000
	Unmarried	10	15.6		

Significant level at <0.05

Table-6 showed the association between WMSDs and socio- demographic variables. It was observed that age, professional qualification, number of children the respondents have, marital status have statistically significant association with the WMSDs as $\chi^2=14.318$, $p=0.003$; $\chi^2= 3.781$, $p=0.05$; $\chi^2= 2.231$, $p=0.013$; and $\chi^2=14.937$, $p=0.000$ respectively. (Need to place below table no.6)

The association of WMSDs with occupational profile of nurses was analyzed using Chi square test and it was found that type of ward, years of experience, working hours per day like occupational variables has no significant relationship with WMSDs as shown in **Table - 7**.

Table-7: Association between Occupational profiles of nurses with WMSDs

Occupation profile		WMSDs present		Chi square	P value
		No.	%		
Ward	General ward	35	54.7	2.689	0.442
	ICU/CCU	11	17.2		
	Casualty	9	14.1		
	OT	9	14.1		
Current year of experience (in years)	0-2	20	31.2	6.836	0.077
	2-4	19	29.7		
	4-6	13	20.3		
	>6	12	18.8		
Total experience in years (in years)	3-10	29	45.3	6.563	0.087
	11-12	26	40.6		
	>20	9	14.1		
Patient assigned per day	1-15	12	21.4	3.413	0.332
	> 15	44	78.6		
Working hours per day	8-10	21	32.8	7.125	0.068
	10-12	8	12.5		
	12-14	21	33.8		
	>14	14	21.9		

Significant level at <0.05

Table- 8: Association of health profile and life style pattern of hospital nurses with WMSD's

Table-8 showed that BMI and level of tiredness among health profile of the nurses have significant association with WMSDs as $\chi^2=11.456$, $p=0.009$; and as $\chi^2=11.910$, $p=0.008$ respectively and none of the life style pattern variable had significant association with WMSDs.

Health profile		WMSDs present		Chi square	P value
		No.	%		
BMI	18.5-25	39	60.9	11.456	0.009
	25-30	25	39.1		
Hemoglobin	8-10 mg/dl	22	34.4	2.477	0.290
	12-14mg/dl	42	65.6		
Health Status (self reported)	Good	49	76.6	2.535	0.282
	Average	15	23.4		
Tiredness	Not tired	8	12.5	11.910	0.008
	A bit tired	18	28.1		
	Tired	33	51.6		
	Very tired	5	7.8		
Recent health complains	Present	11	17.2	1.224	0.269
	Absent	53	82.8		
Any chronic disease	Present	13	20.3	1.497	0.221
	Absent	51	79.7		
Suffered from any injury	Yes	2	3.1	0.193	0.660
	No	62	96.9		
Physical activity	Jogging	21	33.3	5.313	0.150
	Yoga	8	12.7		
	Exercise	25	39.7		
	Other	9	14.3		
Activities for leisure time	Indoor activity	47	73.4	0.127	0.522
	Outdoor activity	17	26.6		

Sleeping Hours	6 hours.	36	56.2	1.276	0.735
	7 hours.	20	31.2		
	>8 hours.	8	12.8		

Section- 4 : Association between risk factors and WMSDs.

Table-9: Association of work condition related variables with WMSDs

Work conditions		WMSDs present		Chi square	P value
Standing for long period	Yes	61	95.3	0.294	0.588
	No	3	4.7		
Sitting for long period	Yes	34	53.1	0.021	0.883
	No	30	46.9		
Moving heavy loads	Yes	16	25	0.199	0.655
	No	48	75		
Exertion of arms/ hands	Yes	49	76.6	0.143	0.706
	No	15	23.4		
Working in uncomfortable position	Yes	53	82.8	0.946	0.331
	No	11	17.2		
Working in same position for long period	Yes	53	82	0.001	0.974
	No	11	17.2		
Climb stair	Yes	61	95.3	1.461	0.227
	No	3	4.7		
Walk on irregular surface	Yes	13	20.3	2.742	0.98
	No	51	79.7		
Working with vibrating tools	Yes	3	4.7	6.787	0.009
	No	61	95.3		
Insufficient space to do work	Yes	35	54.7	0.049	0.826
	No	29	45.3		
Reach the things placed at insufficient height	Yes	4	6.2	0.897	0.343
	No	60	93.8		
Slip or fall during work	Yes	9	14.1	0.968	0.325
	No	55	85.9		
Working area is over-crowded with cords	Yes	14	21.9	0.408	0.523
	No	50	78.1		
Physical status of floor	Slippery	23	35.9	0.904	0.342
	Non slippery	41	64.1		

Significance level is p<0.05 add

The association of work condition related variable and WMSDs was depicted in **table-9** and it was found that only working with vibrating tool is having association with WMSDs.

Discussion

Individuals involved in the nursing profession are more susceptible to the WMSDs. In this study 64(91.58%) hospital nurses out of 70(100%) had reported pain and discomfort in any of these nine body regions(lower back, knees, shoulder, neck, ankle /feet, upper back, hip/ thigh, wrist/hand and elbows).

Among those 64-hospital nurses, the commonest region of pain and discomfort was found in low back (64.3%), then in knees (52.9%) and then in shoulder (42.9%). Whereas least pain and discomfort found in elbow i.e., in 5.7% of subjects. The similar results are reported in a study conducted by Brien et al (2018) on nurses working with patients with spinal cord injuries (PWSCI) in South Africa which showed high cases of lower back complaints in the last 12 months, followed by complaints of the shoulders, knees and ankles or feet.²³ The high frequency of lower back pain in nurses working with patients suffering with spinal

cord injuries may be attributed to the repetitive patient handling tasks required of this specialized group of nurses and a high workload. These results are further supported by similar findings reported by Tinubu et al. (2010) in Nigeria, who founded that the lower back to be the most commonly affected body region (44.1%), followed by the neck (28.0%), and knees (22.4%)²⁴. Attar (2014) found similar results with the lower back (65.7%), ankles/feet (41.5%) and shoulders (29.0%) being the top three most affected body regions¹⁶. These findings are in contrast with a study done by Nkhata et al. (2015), where researchers found ankles and feet to be the most commonly affected body region with a frequency of 54.8%.²⁵

The finding of the study showed that there was significant relationship with age, marital status, number of children, and professional qualification of nurses with WMSDs. The result of study conducted by Kalkim et al indicated correlation between personal attributes and WMSDs, most WMSDs locations were related to age. Age was a predictor of right shoulder and upper back discomfort, with nurses aged 30 years or older having a higher risk than those who were younger than 30 years.²⁶ The results of this study differ from those reported by Yang et al., who discovered that younger service personnel were at higher risk.²⁷ The reason may be because younger service personnel have less refined nursing skills and less precise care actions, resulting in higher risk of waist pain.

The finding of study revealed that there is significant association (at $p < 0.05$) between health-related risk factors like BMI, level of tiredness and WMSDs. The above finding is supported by the study conducted by Yasobant S and Rajkumar. P. (2014) on assessment of WMSDs among health care professionals which reveals that overweight and obese professionals have greater chance of developing WMSDs.²⁸

It was also evident from the study that there was no significant relationship between life style pattern like physical activity, activity in leisure time, sleeping hours and WMSDs. The above finding is different from the findings of the study conducted by Yasobant S and Rajkumar P (2014) on WMSDs among health care professionals. This study shows that life style patterns are 1.85 times responsible for developing WMSDs.²⁸

Other finding of the study was that there was no significant relationship between work condition and WMSDs except working with vibrating tools. A study conducted by Tinibu B Met al (2010) on WMSDs among nurses of selected hospital in Ibadan, South West Nigeria revealed that working in same position for long period (55.1%), lifting or transferring dependent patients (50.8%) and treating an excessive patient in one day (44.9%) were most perceived job risk factors for WMSDs though our finding does not reveal it.²⁴

Limitation

-) The information collected is based on perception of respondent.
-) Like all other cross-sectional or self-report studies, it is possible that our respondents might have given vague answers or exaggerated their WMSDs.
-) The research included a small sample of nurses from Tertiary care hospital of Eastern Uttar Pradesh so the data findings cannot be generalized to the population.

Implication

There is need to prevent WMSDs among hospital nurses as it greatly affects the working system and create hindrance in providing quality care to the patients. To accomplish this goal meticulous efforts are needed in planning preventive programs, training and health education for the target group which guarantee better health for workers as well as increases the productivity and also contribute to reduce the cost and burdens caused due to absenteeism.

Conclusion

From the study it is evident that the prevalence of WMSDs is high among the nurses of tertiary care hospital in Varanasi i.e., 94%. The highest prevalence of pain or discomfort to the low back, knee, shoulder area followed by neck. There was significant association between age, marital status, number of children and professional qualification of nurses and WMSDs. The health-related factors like BMI and tiredness have significant association with WMSDs. In work condition, climbing stairs and

working, in insufficient space were found more prevalent among hospital nurse but working with vibrating tools was found as main risk factors as there was significant association with WMSDs in the study.

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